

GENERAL TERMS FOR WOMEN'S CLOTHING

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These terms can be called the main terms because all other terms are built on them. Let's start with simple textile terms that represent women's clothing in English: robe - women's dress; coat - jacket, uniform, jacket, jacket, outerwear, coat; vest - front attachment (in women's clothing); bolero - short jacket with or without sleeves, bolero; blouse - work blouse, blouse; pantalets - long women's pants; paletot - a loose, wide coat; costume - clothing, dress, style of clothing, costume; tailcoat - women's or children's clothing; cloak - cloak, mantle; corset - corset; skirt - skirt; bowler - hard felt hat; carulet - a female headdress worn on the back of the head; pannier - pannier (part of the skirt); trousers - trousers; pants - socks; waist - corsage, corsage; mantle - counter; jacket - jacket; sheath - a tight, figure-hugging dress; tunic - blouse or jacket, tunic.

There are not a few such simple terms for women's clothing in English, but the Tajik language is no exception.

Here are some examples of textile terms in Tajik for women's clothing: kamzul - kamzulga; hook - braid; kurta - shirt; Homa is a robe made of cotton; chapon - a cotton tunic; rumor - handkerchief; tuppi - skull cap; kafsh - galoshes made of patent leather; faranjī - faranji; durra - a small scarf; kars - white scarf; loci - thin white matter; yaktak - a yellow-striped cloak made of white cotton; gentleman - woolen socks; kur - a woven ribbon with a pattern; hat - flat round cap; quvd - boots with soft soles; lahak - a piece of cloth covering the neck, the lower corners of which are folded towards the middle.

From the examples given, it is clear that the number of simple terms related to women's clothing in the compared languages is greater than all other classes in terms of structure.

In the Tajik language, the model of complex structural terms is the most developed, and it is easier to determine the structure of complex terms, since the largest number of terms is original. For example: sarandoz - a tulle blanket for the bride's head (from the words sar and andoz); poihoma - prosperous (from the words song and goma); chashmband - a hair net that a woman should put on her face under a burqa (from the words chashm and band); ezorband - braid for tying flowerbeds; dastrumol - scarf (from the words ber and römöl); tustuppi - a doppi with a flat square top (from the words tus and tuppi); peshonaband - gold-plated headband (from the words peshona and tasma); sarostin - sleeve cuffs decorated with a cross stitch (from the words sar and austin); sargirak - a light flowing robe-shaped women's headdress with a tunic-like cut. Derived terms are the direct components of complex word forms, which are morphological formants - prefixes and suffixes. Let's see how the affixes denoting women's clothing work in textile terms.

In English, there are derivational terms formed using the suffix -ic. An example of such a word-formation in English is cambric, a very fine linen used for making shirts and dresses, forming the diminutive form of the word - ic .

In the Tajik language, diminutive suffixes are also used to form textile terms for women's clothing. Such suffixes are -ak and -cha. For example, a vest or a shirt is a sleeveless vest that is long up to the middle of the thigh; rumcha - a robe made of local silk of the kanausa type; short - vest; durracha - a small scarf; munisak - a turban hanging on the waist and folded on the side; gelak - a traditional tunic-shaped opening robe; Teapot - bib made of white cotton; Lachak is a headdress of old women.

From the examples given in the compared languages, it can be easily determined that the use of diminutive suffixes in Tajik is more derivative than in English.

The structural analysis of terms in the dictionary of women's clothing showed that the system of word formation in the compared languages is a unique feature. For example, phrases are more effective as a way of forming words in English than in Tajik. For example, blue jeans, chanel suit, top, morning dress, denim jacket, trench coat, stretch skinny pants, wool jacket with side zipper, etc., affixation and conjunction are most effective in Tajik language.

It should be noted that the structural analysis of clothing vocabulary terms in comparable languages can also be carried out using the partial structure of complex terms. Based on this structure, the following models can be distinguished: Horse - horse. In Tajik, this model includes terms such as poyoma (from the nouns poy and joma), daströmöl (from the nouns datus and rumöl), sarostin (from the nouns sar and ostin), bugoma (from the nouns bug and joma). , and others. In English, the model noun is a noun. refers to the terms gilet (from the nouns waist and coat) and rain (from the nouns rain and coat); A noun is a verb. This model is typical of the Tajik language. For example, sarandoz (from the verb sar and andoz), chashmband (from the verb chashm and toda), peshonaband (from the noun peshona and the verb toda) and so on. In English, there is no defined term for such a model. Adjective is a noun. The conditions of this type of model are mainly related to the English language. For example, the term big coat consists of the adjective big and the noun coat;

In the languages being compared, you can also find phrases in which one of the components is always repeated in different combinations.

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